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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of the research described in this document is to provide an assessment of the hazard of jet engine exhaust. This has been done based on available literature and newly generated experimental data. A literature survey was performed, which was focussed on 1) the physical and chemical composition of jet engine emissions, and 2) the toxicity of jet engine exhaust. Composition and hazard data extracted from the literature are presented in an open-access Excel-based database, appended to and summarized in this report. To support the hazard assessment, particulate matter from jet engine exhaust was collected and analyzed for oxidative potential as an indicator for toxicity.

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List of Abbreviations

AAdep	ascorbic acid depletion
ARO	aromatic compounds
AtJ	alcohol to jet
AU	arbitrary unit
BAL	broncho-alveolar lavage
BTEX	benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylene
CAST	Combustion Aerosol STandard
CB	carbon black
CO	carbon monoxide
CO ₂	carbon dioxide
DEP	diesel exhaust particles
DOFA	Diesel Oil Fly Ash
DMPO	5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline-N-oxide
DTT	dithiothreitol
DTNB	5,5'-dithiobis-(2-) nitrobenzoic acid
EC	elemental carbon
EI	emission index
ESR	electron spin resonance
FEV1	forced expiratory volume in one second
FVC	forced vital capacity
H ₂ O ₂	hydrogen peroxide
HEFA	hydroprocessed esters and fatty acids
HPLC	high-performance liquid chromatography
IHD	ischemic heart disease
IL-6 (or -8)	interleukin-6 (or -8)
JEP	jet engine particles
LDH	lactate dehydrogenase
LTO	Landing/Take-Off cycle
MMAD	median aerodynamic diameter
NO _x	nitrogen oxides
OC	organic carbon
OP	oxidative potential
PAH	polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PBS	phosphate buffered saline
PM	particulate matter
PTFE	polytetrafluoroethylene
ROS	reactive oxygen species
S	sulfur
SAF	sustainable aviation fuel
SO ₂	sulphur dioxide
SPK	synthetic paraffinic kerosene
sTNFRII	soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor type II
TNF- α	tumor necrosis factor- α
UFP	ultrafine particles
VOCs	volatile organic compounds

WHO World Health Organisation

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1 Introduction

Particulate matter (PM) in the air can have harmful effects on health. The European Union therefore set limit values for particulate matter (PM₁₀) in 1999. In 2008, the regulations were extended to include limit and target values for the finer fraction of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). Internationally accepted insights about the health effects of particulate matter are contained in these regulations. The European air quality standards have been translated into national legislation. Recently, WHO also noted that ultrafine particles (UFP, <100 nm, Figure 1) will be of concern but that there is a lack of scientific information to derived guideline values. Albeit that UFP can be measured also by mass, a more commonly used metric is number counts due to the relative low mass of UFP in the entire PM mixture whereas it by far dominates the number counts (Figure 1).

PM emissions from aircraft engines adversely affect air quality in and around airports, contributing to public health concerns for airport workers and within neighboring communities. One of the research goals of RAPTOR is to retrieve a more nuanced understanding of the potential impact of particles and specifically UFP as those small particles are mainly emitted by jet engines. Very little information is available from peer reviewed literature regarding the health effects of emissions from jet engines. There are no health-based standards for UFP in ambient air. PM is controlled based on particles smaller than 10 μm (based on mass median aerodynamic diameter; MMAD) or 2.5 μm . Although this includes UFP, the mass of these UFP is often negligible compared to the rest of the mixture. Focusing only on PM_{2.5} may result in overlooking the impact of UFP.

Figure 1: The top showing fine particle number distribution and the bottom showing fine particle volume distribution (Chapter 8 in Environment Canada and U.S. Environmental Protection Agency 2014).

As a rule of thumb, the smaller the particles the deeper they penetrate into the lung. Inhalation of airborne particles will lead to deposition onto the regional epithelia of the respiratory tract. The actual deposition depends on (1) the aerodynamic, diffusional and

thermodynamic properties of the particles and only on the latter two for UFP; (2) the geometric branching pattern of the individual airways and alveoli, and (3) on the breathing pattern of the human (Oberdorster, Oberdorster et al. 2005, Kreyling, Semmler-Behnke et al. 2006, Moller, Felten et al. 2008, Moller, Meyer et al. 2009) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Fractional deposition of inhaled particles in the nasopharyngeal, tracheobronchial, and alveolar region of the respiratory tract during nose breathing (from Oberdorster et al. 2005).

Irrespective of the hazard of the material, the implications for human health are also related to the dose that is deposited in the respiratory system, with smaller particles having a higher likelihood to reach the alveoli, the area where gas exchange (oxygen, carbon dioxide) takes place. In addition, the size also affects the way the human host defence system is dealing with the material, with again the nano-sized particles having the properties to escape this and penetrate the biological barriers and reach the systemic circulation which is not seen for micron sized particles in that extent.

Adverse health effects of the particles are strongly linked to their size, which is a determinant (in a probabilistic sense) of their fate in the air and their potential of toxicity. UFP constitute a health risk, due to their specific properties such as high number concentration and surface area, high deposition efficiency in the pulmonary region where they can cause inflammation, and a high propensity to penetrate the epithelium and translocate to the blood system. As a

result, UFP may cause a variety of diseases. The impacts of UFP may increase in the future due to changes in the use of fuel as well as in the increase in the number of emission sources (e.g. aircraft) and due to the decrease of large particles (which in turn can favour UFP formation) through control and abatement measures.

The precise mechanism of UFP in causing health problems is still mostly unknown (Schraufnagel 2020). Latest studies suggest that many different health problems could be associated to the exposure to short-term and long-term high UFP concentrations, albeit that there is no evidence for a complete independent effect from those associated with PM_{2.5} (HEI Review Panel on Ultrafine Particles 2013, U.S. EPA 2019, Schraufnagel 2020).

The capacity of PM to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), known as “oxidative potential” (OP) is suggested to be one of the most relevant indicators of PM toxicity. Many relevant toxic effects of PM might be triggered through PM-induced oxidative stress due to ROS generation in cells. In particular, small particle size and PM species including elemental carbon (EC), a number of organics and soluble transition metals can have significant effects on the toxicity of PM (Aust, Ball et al. 2002, Kelly and Fussell 2012, Loxham, Cooper et al. 2013). However, further research is needed to investigate the ROS-mediated mechanism(s) of toxicity in relation to the physico-chemical properties of PM.

Some studies are starting to explore health problems related to aviation’s UFP emissions. Barrett, Britter et al. (2010) estimated that around 8000 premature mortalities were attributable to aircraft cruise emissions globally every year. Touri, Marchetti et al. (2013) examined the impact of airport pollution exposure on respiratory health by evaluation of studies on occupational exposure. Although the link between respiratory health effects and airport pollution exposure was shown in a few occupational studies, the correlation was weak and needs further research. Therefore, understanding the associated risks of exposure to airport-related PM in comparison with other major contributors to urban PM such as vehicle emissions are of great significance to public health officials and legislators.

The aim of the present work was to assess the hazard of jet engine exhaust, based on available literature and newly generated experimental data. A literature survey was performed which was focussed on 1) the physical and chemical composition of jet engine emissions, and 2) the toxicity of jet engine exhaust. Exposure variables as well as engine settings and operating conditions were tabulated (as far as available) to allow for an assessment of critical factors that affect the hazard of the emission mixture. In addition, the published toxicity data on jet engine emissions were put in perspective of toxicity data of road traffic PM emissions. The hazard and composition data extracted from the literature are presented in an open-access Excel-based database and summarized in this report. To support the hazard assessment, measurements of the Oxidative Potential (OP) of collected PM samples were performed. Oxidative potential measurements of PM samples – with reference to information available from literature – could help to provide a more nuanced understanding of the potential health impact of jet engine PM emissions, without the need to use cells, tissues, animals, or humans.

2 Methodology

2.1 Literature survey

2.1.1 Physical and chemical composition of aircraft emissions

The collection of relevant literature concerning the physical and chemical characterization of aircraft emissions was performed utilizing the abstract and citation database “Scopus” (www.scopus.com). The scope of relevant literature was based on prior knowledge on PM emissions and discussions with scientists and a toxicologist. Within this scope of literature of interest are scientific papers which contain information about aircraft emissions in combination with at least one of the following subjects:

- (Ultrafine) particulate matter
- Elemental carbon
- Organic carbon
- Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)
- Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)
- Carbonyl or aldehyde compounds

The search string used in Scopus was: (TITLE (aircraft)) AND ((TITLE-ABS (emissions))) AND ("particulate matter" OR ultrafine OR "elemental carbon" OR "organic carbon" OR "volatile organic compound" OR voc OR pah OR "poly aromatic hydrocarbon" OR carbonyl OR aldehyde). The abstracts of the hits obtained with this search string were subsequently screened for relevance, and only literature that contained analytical data on aircraft exhaust emissions were selected.

2.1.2 Toxicity of aircraft emissions

The literature search of the toxicity of aircraft emission was performed by information specialists and reviewed by two toxicologists. Searches were performed in two abstract and citation databases: Scopus (www.scopus.com) and Embase (www.embase.com) (Table 1). Duplicates were removed and the abstracts of the hits obtained with these search strings were subsequently screened for relevance. In-house expertise was consulted for the recent relevant literature on road traffic PM toxicity for comparison.

The search query used in Scopus was: (TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH ('health*' OR 'adverse-event*' OR 'toxic*' OR 'carcinogenicity' OR 'inflamm*')) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH ('expos*' OR 'oxide' OR 'hydrocarbon*' OR 'nanopartic*' OR 'ultrafine' OR 'hydrocarbon*' OR 'volatile-organic-compound*' OR 'air-pollut*' OR 'exhaust' OR 'emission*' OR 'air-pollutant*' OR 'fume' OR 'particulate-matter*')) AND ((TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH ('aircraft*' OR 'airplane*' OR 'aeroplane*' OR 'airport' OR 'jet')) OR ((TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH ('turbines' OR 'turbofan*' OR 'turboprop*')) AND NOT (TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH ('wind-turbine*')))) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH ('cfm56*' OR 'jt8d*' OR 'cf6*' OR 'v2528*' OR 'v2500*' OR 'pw4000*' OR 'pw6000*' OR 'a320*' OR 'cf34*' OR 'jt3d*' OR 'rb211*' OR '3007-a1e*' OR 'pratt-whitney-4158*' OR 'c-t53-l-13b*' OR 'f100*' OR 't63-a-700*' OR 'allison-t56*')))

Table 1: Search query and results for Embase

No.	Query	Results
#25	#24 NOT 'noise*':ti	84
#24	#18 OR #19 OR #23	96
#23	#17 AND #22	4
#22	#10 AND #21	34
#21	#20 AND ('engine*':ti,ab OR 'jet*':ti,ab OR 'aircraft*':ti,ab OR 'combustion*':ti,ab)	51
#20	'cfm56*':ti,ab OR 'jt8d*':ti,ab OR 'cf6*':ti,ab OR 'v2528*':ti,ab OR 'v2500*':ti,ab OR 'pw4000*':ti,ab OR 'pw6000*':ti,ab OR 'a320*':ti,ab OR 'cf34*':ti,ab OR 'jt3d*':ti,ab OR 'rb211*':ti,ab OR '3007-a1e*':ti,ab OR 'pratt-whitney 4158*':ti,ab OR 'c-t53-l-13b*':ti,ab OR 'f100*':ti,ab OR 't63-a-700*':ti,ab OR 'allison t56*':ti,ab	616
#19	#12 AND #17	21
#18	#11 AND #17	81
#17	#13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16	6466919
#16	'health'/exp	754982
#15	((('respiratory' OR 'health*' OR 'adverse') NEAR/3 ('effect*' OR 'risk*' OR 'event*' OR 'react*'))):ti,ab	891860
#14	'health hazard'/exp OR 'adverse event'/exp	1285862
#13	'toxicity'/exp OR 'carcinogenicity'/exp OR 'inflammation'/exp	4423507
#12	#4 AND #10	439
#11	#3 AND #10	566
#10	#5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9	5544881
#9	'particulate matter exposure'/exp OR 'exposure'/mj OR 'dust exposure'/exp OR 'expos*':ti	276273
#8	'oxide'/exp OR 'hydrocarbon'/exp	4983079
#7	'nanoparticl*':ti OR 'ultrafine':ti OR 'hydrocarbon'/exp OR 'volatile organic compound'/exp	4146185
#6	'air pollut*':ti OR 'exhaust':ti OR 'emission*':ti	88717
#5	'air pollutant'/exp OR 'fume'/exp OR 'exhaust gas'/exp OR 'particulate matter'/exp OR 'nanoparticle'/exp	466219
#4	('turbines':ti,ab OR 'turbofan*':ti,ab OR 'turboprop*':ti,ab OR (((('turbine' OR 'turbines') NEAR/3 ('engine*' OR 'combust*' OR 'emission*'))):ti,ab)) NOT 'wind turbine*':ti	1282
#3	#1 AND #2	2325
#2	'aircraft*':ti OR 'airplane*':ti OR 'aeroplane*':ti OR 'airport':ti OR 'jet':ti	11954
#1	'aircraft'/exp/mj OR 'airport'/exp/mj	5543

2.2 PM sampling

2.2.1 Sampling procedure

In order to be able to compare the collected PM from different sampling locations, a standardized PM sampling procedure was formulated. A PM10 sampling device (provided by TNO) with a 47 mm alumina sampling head was used for in-line sampling (maximum flow rate

of 80 L/min). The actual flow rate was determined at the start and end of the sampling period, and the sampling time was recorded. Air velocity through the sampler was adjusted to the air velocity in the tunnel to ensure isokinetic sampling. PTFE Membrane Filters ($\varnothing = 47$ mm) with a pore size of 1 μm (Fluoropore, provided by TNO, and coded “EU-xx”) and 2 μm (Pall Corporation, provided by RIVM, and coded “RAPTOR-xx”) were used for sampling. Target particle load was 1-2 mg per filter. Loaded filters were stored in petri dishes, in the dark and below 7°C. After sampling, filters were transported (in the dark and below 7°C) to TNO where the filters were stored at -20°C.

2.2.2 Overview collected PM samples

Table 2: PM samples collected by ONERA during the UNREAL (Unveiling Nucleation mechanism in aircraft Engine exhaust and its Link with fuel composition) campaign:

Experiment number	Sampling date	Fuel type	Aromatic content (%)	Sulfur content (ppm)	Sample code
1	23-11-2020	Jet A1 High aromatic compounds (ARO) & high sulfur (S) compounds	23	3000	RAPTOR 1
2	23-11-2020	Jet A1 High ARO, high S	23	3000	RAPTOR 2
3	24-11-2020	Alcohol to Jet (AtJ)	0	0	RAPTOR 3
4	25-11-2020	Jet A1 High ARO	23	4	RAPTOR 4
5	27-11-2020	Jet A1 High S	16	3000	EU-04
6	27-11-2020	Jet A1 High S	16	3000	RAPTOR 6
7	2-12-2020	Blank	-	-	EU-21
8	3-12-2020	Jet A1 High ARO	23	4	EU-23
9	3-12-2020	Jet A1 reference	16	4	EU-42
10	3-12-2020	Jet A1 reference	16	4	RAPTOR 7
11	4-12-2020	Blank of line	-	-	EU-43
12	7-12-2020	Jet A1	16	200	EU-51
13	7-12-2020	Jet A1	16	200	RAPTOR 9
14	8-12-2020	Jet A1/ AtJ blend	10.8	140	EU-53
15	8-12-2020	Jet A1/ AtJ blend	10.8	140	RAPTOR 10
16	9-12-2020	Jet A1 High ARO, high S	23	3000	RAPTOR 11
17	9-12-2020	Jet A1 High ARO, high S	23	3000	EU-55
18	10-12-2020	SPK	2.5	0	EU-60
19	10-12-2020	SPK	2.5	0	RAPTOR 12

ARO: aromatic compounds; S: sulfur compounds; AtJ: alcohol to Jet; SPK: synthetic paraffinic kerosene
PTFE filters coded “RAPTOR xx” were supplied by RIVM; filters coded “EU-xx” were supplied by TNO.

The sampling of these filters was done in parallel to a measurement campaign performed in the frame of the UNREAL project. The objective of the UNREAL project is to study the formation of volatile particles from combustion exhaust and to link this with fuel composition. During the campaign, a Combustion Aerosol Standard (CAST) generator was used, which is especially designed to work with liquid fuel. Fuels with different composition, from the standard Jet-A1 to 100% Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF; Alcohol to Jet) were tested. CAST raw emissions (unaged) were sampled and characterized. A total number of 19 filter samples were

collected for analysis of oxidative potential (OP), comprising 2 blank filters and 17 PM filters obtained from different fuel types (Table 2). Blank EU-21 was left overnight in the filter holder; the “blank of line” (EU-43) was sampled without the sampling line connected to the CAST generator. For OP measurements, 3 additional untreated blank filters (EU-57, RAPTOR 5, RAPTOR 8) were included. Details of the sampling campaign are included in Annex 1.

In parallel to sampling of the filters for OP analysis, simultaneous physicochemical analysis of the CAST emission was performed. Non-volatile particle mass and number concentrations and particle size for each Jet-A1 fuel are summarized in the Table 3.

Table 3: Emissions characterization for each jet-A1 fuel tested

Fuel type	Particle number concentration (#/cm ³)	Particle mass concentration (mg/m ³)	Geometric mean diameter (nm)
Jet A1 High ARO, high S	5.74 · 10 ⁷	590.18	113.4
Jet A1 High S	5.53 · 10 ⁷	442.44	97.2
Jet A1 High ARO	8.37 · 10 ⁷	643.02	108.3
Jet A1 reference	4.65 · 10 ⁷	326.75	101.0

In addition; filters were collected for off-line analysis using Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) of CAST emissions (reference fuel and high sulfur / high aromatic fuel only). This technique allows the characterization of different compounds present in the sample. Sulfur containing compounds, polycyclic aromatics hydrocarbons (PAH) and volatile organic compounds (VOC) were identified (Table 4). This technique is not quantitative, but can be used to estimate the relative abundance of each compound in the different samples.

Table 4: Compounds identified using Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry

Name	Formula	m/z
PAH		
Naphtalene	C ₁₀ H ₈	128.06
Acenaphtylene	C ₁₂ H ₈	152.06
Acenaphtene	C ₁₂ H ₁₀	154.08
Fluorene	C ₁₃ H ₁₀	166.08
Antracene	C ₁₄ H ₁₀	178.08
Phenanthrene	C ₁₄ H ₁₀	178.08
Fluoranthene	C ₁₆ H ₁₀	202.08
Pyrene	C ₁₆ H ₁₀	202.08
Benzo(a)anthracene	C ₁₈ H ₁₂	228.09
Chrysene	C ₁₈ H ₁₂	228.09
Benzo(a)pyrene	C ₂₀ H ₁₂	252.09
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	C ₂₀ H ₁₂	252.09
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	C ₂₀ H ₁₂	252.09
Benzo(ghi)perylene	C ₂₀ H ₁₂	252.09
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	C ₂₂ H ₁₂	276.09
Dibenzoanthracene	C ₂₂ H ₁₄	278.11

Sulfur containing compounds		
Sulfur dioxide	SO ₂	63.96
Hydrogenosulfite	HSO ₂	64.97
Sulfur trioxyde	SO ₃	79.95
Hydrogenosulfite	HSO ₃	80.96
Hydrogenosulfate	HSO ₄	96.96
VOC		
Acetylene	C ₂ H ₂	26.01
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	28.03
Propene	C ₃ H ₆	42.05
Benzene	C ₆ H ₆	78.05
Toluene	C ₇ H ₈	92.06
Ethylbenzene	C ₈ H ₁₀	106.078
Xylene	C ₈ H ₁₀	106.078

Figure 3 depicts the relative abundance for each sample of the different families of compounds detected. Carbon clusters correspond to the black carbon forming the soot particles. In general, the sample from the fuel containing higher amounts of sulfur and aromatics presented a higher amount of PAHs, VOC and sulfur containing compounds, while the one from the reference fuel contained more carbon clusters. This indicates that the ratio elemental carbon (EC) to organic carbon (OC) is higher for the sample coming from the fuel containing more aromatic compounds and sulfur. The differences is especially noticeable for PAHs, where the sample from reference fuel contains almost eight time less PAHs than the sample coming from the fuel with higher amounts of sulfur and aromatic compounds.

Figure 3: Comparison of the relative abundance of each family of compounds identified in the samples analyzed

In addition to the abovementioned filters obtained by ONERA, further PM samples were collected by Cardiff University (see Table 5). The PM filters were sampled utilizing a generic Rich Quench Lean (RQL) combustor rig developed and operated by Cardiff University's Gas Turbine Research Centre (GTRC). Details of the RQL experimental setup can be found in RAPTOR deliverable 4.1. All tests were performed at 3 bar on the normal drive line.

Table 5: PM samples collected by Cardiff University

Experiment number	Sampling date	Fuel type	Total aromatics (%)	Hydrogen content (%)	H/C ratio	Sample code
1	-	Filter blank	-	-	-	EU-01
2	1-3-2021	Blank of line	-	-	-	EU-31
3	26-2-2021	SAF J2 (F4)	12.82	14.49	2.027	EU-33
4	21-2-2021	Jet A	24.24	13.427	1.861	EU-35
5	26-2-2021	B3	25.18	13.48	1.864	EU-39
6	26-2-2021	F1	22.75	13.66	1.896	EU-41
7	26-2-2021	75% GTL	6.71	14.895	2.100	EU-45
8	26-2-2021	100% GTL	0.06	15.47	2.196	EU-47
9	26-2-2021	B3	25.18	13.48	1.864	EU-49

The filter blank (EU-01) was shipped to (but not touched by) GTRC and kept in the original shipping box; the blank of line (EU-31) was placed in a filter holder (without actual sampling), removed and subsequently handled and stored like the loaded filters. A brief description of the fuel types is also given below (for details see RAPTOR D4.1):

- 1) SAF J2 (new designator for F4): Low sulphur Jet-A fuel (70%) mixed with HEFA fuel (30%)
- 2) Jet A: High aromatic Jet-A fuel
- 3) B3: Catalytic Hydrothermal Conversion Jet (CHCJ) fuel
- 4) F1: High Di-aromatic Jet-A fuel
- 5) 100% GTL: Low aromatic Fischer Tropsch (FT) Gas-To-Liquid (GTL) fuel derived from natural gas
- 6) 75% GTL: GTL (75 %) (5) and 25% Jet-A fuel (2).

2.3 PM extraction

The filters used for collecting the materials by ONERA and Cardiff University were handed over by TNO to RIVM where they were stored at -80°C until extraction. The filters were stored in individual filterholders to prevent contamination.

The filters were extracted one by one. The filter was transferred to a clean petridish and 2 mL HPLC-grade methanol (BioSolve BV, Valkenswaard, the Netherlands; art.no. 136806) was added. The petridish was held a couple of millimeters in the ultrasonic bath above the center point of the sonic burst for 30 seconds. This was done carefully to prevent water contamination. Afterwards the petridish was tilted approximately 30 degrees, and the supernatant was transferred into a preweighed and correctly labelled cryovial. The filter was flipped over with a clean plastic tweezer and the extraction step was repeated with fresh methanol. The methanol suspension was transferred into the same cryovial.

The extracted solution was dried overnight at 25°C in an incubator. This was done under a constant flow of nitrogen to prevent further PM degradation or oxidation.

The cryovials with the extracts were reweighed to calculate the extraction yield. The PM-containing vials were stored at -20°C until further processing, e.g. oxidative potential measurements.

2.4 Measurement of oxidative potential

The oxidative potential (OP) of the PM samples was measured using three markers: dithiothreitol (DTT) formation, electron spin resonance (ESR) and ascorbic acid (AA) depletion. Each assay has a different sensitivity to different types of ROS generating compounds (Calas et al. 2018). In the DTT assay, redox-active chemicals in PM oxidize added DTT to its disulfide form and the rate of DTT loss is used as a measure for the oxidative capacity of the PM. Redox-active species in PM then donate an electron to dissolved oxygen, forming superoxide which in turn can form other reactive oxygen species (ROS). ESR measures the ability of PM to induce hydroxyl radicals in the presence of H₂O₂. The AA depletion assay measures the ability of PM to deplete the antioxidant ascorbic acid. ESR and AA depletion have been shown to be most sensitive to transition metals (Calas et al. 2018). For DTT, typically compounds which react are organic species (e.g polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and quinones), but studies have also shown that high concentrations of transition metal ions can oxidize DTT (Charrier and Anastasio 2012).

For OP measurements, the PM extracts (stored at -20°C) were resuspended in ultrapure water. The ESR and DTT assays were performed using PM suspensions of 1 mg/mL; for the Ascorbic Acid Depletion assay, these suspensions were further diluted to 12.5 µg/mL in ultrapure water.

2.4.1 DTT assay

The DTT assay determines the general redox activity of a sample by measuring the capacity of the test sample to transfer electrons from dithiothreitol (DTT) to oxygen. During this reaction DTT is consumed.

The subsequent loss of DTT is followed by its reaction with 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-) nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) to form 2-nitro-5-mercaptobenzoic acid, which is monitored spectrophotometrically at 412 nm. The assay was performed as described previously by (Gerlofs-Nijland, Totlandsdal et al. 2013). In the procedure, duplicate samples were incubated for fixed time intervals between 0 and 30 minutes to allow DTT consumption by the particulate matter sample. DTT consumption was determined at four time points and the resulting data were analyzed by linear regression to determine the initial rate of DTT consumption. The results are expressed as consumption of DTT (DTT_{cons}) per mass particulate matter in time (nmol DTT/µg PM*min). Positive (DOFA; Diesel Oil Fly Ash) and negative controls (phosphate-buffered saline, PBS) were included in the assay.

2.4.2 Ascorbic Acid Depletion Assay

The Ascorbic Acid Depletion Assay determines the metal dependent oxidative activity of a particulate matter sample. This is determined by measuring the capacity of a fixed mass of the test sample to consume ascorbic acid.

The subsequent loss of ascorbic acid is followed by its reaction with PM, which is monitored spectrophotometrically at 265 nm (ultraviolet). PM samples were analyzed as described previously by He, Shirmohammadi et al. (2018). In the procedure, duplicate samples were incubated for a fixed time (1.5 hrs) to allow ascorbate consumption by the particulate matter sample. Ascorbic acid consumption was measured every 2 minutes and finally determined by plotting the resulting data which were analyzed by linear regression to determine the initial rate of ascorbic acid consumption. The results ($AA_{dep_{max}}$) are expressed as nmol ascorbic acid consumed per second. Positive (DOFA) and negative controls (PBS) were included in the assay.

2.4.3 Electron spin resonance

Electron spin resonance (ESR) measures the formation of $\cdot OH$ by the collected PM samples in the presence of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and the spin trap 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline-N-oxide (DMPO). This method is mainly sensitive to metal mediated reactive oxygen species, especially $OH\cdot$, by Fenton-type-reactions. The protocol is based on a paper by Hellack, Quass et al. (2015). PM samples were analyzed as described previously by He, Shirmohammadi et al. (2018) using a MS400 Miniscope (Magnettech GmbH, Berlin, Germany). For positive control DOFA and for negative control ultrapure water were used. For all measurements the same amount of sample is used. All results are expressed as the total amplitudes of DMPO-OH quartet in arbitrary units (AU).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Overview literature

3.1.1 Physical and chemical composition

The search for papers in which data on the physicochemical composition have been presented resulted in approximately 450 hits in Scopus. After scanning the abstracts, 103 papers were collected which contain actual information on aircraft emissions. These emission data could be obtained from sampling campaigns at an airport, emissions measurements using an engine test rig, or from research on innovative sampling techniques.

With the literature available, 3 Excel-based databases were created: 1) a crude literature tab which contains information about all 103 relevant papers; 2) a detailed phys-chem literature tab comprising 27 papers; 3) an emission file containing emission indices from different measurement campaigns. For this emission file only 10 papers/reports were finally utilized as input since their actual numerical data could be obtained. This is in sharp contrast to the other (17) potential papers listed in the detailed phys-chem literature file, which only contained graphical representations of the data (important to note is that also the supporting information did not contain numerical data). All 3 databases are included as deliverable for the RAPTOR project (an Excel file containing the crude literature tab, detailed phys-chem tab, combined with tabs describing the toxicity literature; and a separate Excel file containing the emission data).

Crude literature tab

The crude literature database (103 papers) revealed a prominent characteristic: very often the conducted research on aircraft emissions focused either on 1) particulate matter (PM) size distributions and mass in combination with gasses such as CO, CO₂ or NO_x. Or the research focused on 2) the chemical composition of the particulate matter, such as metals or elemental/organic carbon ratio's and in particular the characterization of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) such as polyaromatic hydrocarbons, carbonyls, aliphatic compounds, monoaromatics. In lesser extent this was also reported in combination with data on the emission of various gasses.

Detailed phys-chem literature tab

Since the chemical composition of PM will be the most dominant parameter in assays such as a DTT assay to determine the oxidative potential, it was decided to focus on PM in the chemical composition. From the crude literature database a detailed phys-chem literature tab was constructed, containing detailed information on 27 research papers which were selected based on the variety of measured (organic) compounds. Papers were selected which report the analysis of multiple type of (organic) compounds, or at least report the values for polyaromatic hydrocarbons, in order to derive a literature list which can be used for comparison. The detailed phys-chem tab describes aircraft/engine details, sampling details, physiochemical measurements and offline chemical analysis details. Interesting to note is the large variation of parameters in the different publications when comparing the different

entries in the detailed phys-chem literature tab, making the analytical data difficult to compare. These variations in parameters include:

- A variety of different engine types
- Various fuels (from synthetic fuels (Fischer-Tropsch fuels) to oil-derived fuels)
- Engine mode of operation (from extended LTO cycles to arrive and departure measurements)
- Sampling methods
 - Behind the plane exhaust
 - Utilizing a testing rig
 - Air sampling at an airport
- Sampling techniques
 - Canisters (offline)
 - Filters (offline)
 - Adsorbents (offline)
 - Online chemical characterization
- Chemical characterization (from a limited set of compounds to extensive chemical analysis)

Emission file

As mentioned above, the emission file was constructed utilizing 10 research papers as numerical input. This resulted in a file containing the emission indices of 12 different airplane engines. Per engine, the emission indices for each analyzed compound are sorted vertically and the values for different percentages of thrust are displayed horizontally (Figure 4). Per engine, the results from different fuels are clustered, which allows for the comparison between different fuels.

	Fuel	Jet A			
		percentage of thrust			
		4 - 7 %	30 - 40 %	65 %	85 %
	Unit				
PM2.5	EI (g/kg fuel)	1.56E-02	2.98E-02	1.23E-01	3.29E-01
EC	EI (g/kg fuel)	8.52E-03	2.06E-02	9.07E-02	2.60E-01
OC	EI (g/kg fuel)	1.23E-02	9.77E-03	2.39E-02	6.19E-02
Sulfate	EI (g/kg fuel)	6.88E-04	1.10E-03	2.02E-03	5.57E-03
PAHs					
Naphthalene	EI (g/kg fuel)	2.16E-02	2.18E-01	2.25E+00	1.06E+00
1-Methylnaphthalene	EI (g/kg fuel)	9.01E-04	8.03E-04	6.58E-03	1.33E-03

Figure 4: A snapshot of the emission file

Overall, the collected data are in good agreement with the trends in aircraft emissions in correlation to operation modes or fuel described in a detailed literature review by Masiol and Harrison (2014). For example, they describe the influence of the fuel type on the PM emissions; a typical Fischer-Tropsch fuel has no sulfur and low aromatic content which is found

to be beneficial to reduce the emission of PM and PM precursors. They also reported that the sulfur content is directly related to the SO₂ emissions of an aircraft, but also correlates to sulfate ions which act as nucleation points for PM formation. Furthermore, the correlation between emissions and level of thrust is described. For example, the emission index of CO₂ (EI(CO₂)) decreases at lower engine thrust levels, while the carbon monoxide emissions indices are highest at lower engine thrust levels of the landing-take-off (LTO) cycle. In terms of chemical composition, the total hydrocarbon emission indices are highest at low power settings, where combustor temperatures and pressures are low and combustion is less efficient (Sutkus Jr, Baughcum et al. 2001, Yelvington, Herndon et al. 2007). The emission of carbonyl compounds is significantly higher during the idle mode than at higher thrusts, similar to BTEX compounds which show large decreases in emissions with increasing engine power. For polyaromatic hydrocarbons, Agrawal et al. showed that the lighter congeners such naphthalene and its 1- and 2-methyl derivatives contribute strongly to the total PAH mass in various aircraft emissions at differing thrust modes (Agrawal, Sawant et al. 2008). It was observed that the emission index of naphthalene increased as power increased from idle mode falling off as the engine operated at the highest power.

Although a plethora of research has been conducted on aircraft emissions, knowledge gaps have been described in literature which are still valid today (Transportation Research Board; National Academies of Sciences Engineering Medicine 2008, Lee, Pitari et al. 2010, Masiol and Harrison 2014). For example, the current information on aircraft emissions remains inadequate, since the inclusion of extensive physical and chemical analysis is often limited. Additionally, the knowledge about secondary transformations in aging aircraft exhaust is still in development.

The need for a generalized sampling procedure can also be identified. Currently a lot of different measurement strategies, methodologies and technologies are applied, which lead to data that are difficult to compare. This becomes even more apparent when the toxicity of aircraft emissions will be studied: generalized sampling procedures for collecting particulate matter from aircraft exhaust will be a crucial step towards health impact assessment of (aircraft) emissions.

3.1.2 Toxicity

The search for data on toxicity of emissions from jet engines resulted in 95 hits. After scanning the abstracts, 4 papers were collected with useful information on the toxicity of jet engine particles (JEP). As the literature search resulted in only a few toxicological studies, relevant epidemiological studies and reviews from the literature search were included as well. This resulted in a total of 12 papers. One paper was further added after reading the 12 papers; one paper was added by a consortium member and one paper only had the abstract in English and was not included as the abstract did not contain any measurement data. All relevant papers were described in an Excel-based toxicity database (combined – in separate toxicity tabs – in one Excel file together with the phys-chem literature), and the results are summarized below.

The toxicity data in these papers were generated by *in vitro/in vivo* toxicological experiments using an engine test rig (Ferry, Rolland et al. 2011, He, Shirmohammadi et al. 2018, Jonsdottir, Delaval et al. 2019, He, Gerlofs-Nijland et al. 2020) and/or samples collected near a jet engine

airplane or major airport (He, Shirmohammadi et al. 2018, Bendtsen, Brostrøm et al. 2019, He, Gerlofs-Nijland et al. 2020). The tab on toxicity also contains a recent review on the health effects associated with exposure to jet engine emissions (Bendtsen, Bengtsen et al. 2021). In addition, one paper (Bendtsen, Gren et al. 2020) is added to the database since a similar experimental set-up was used as the only *in vivo* toxicity study of jet engine particles. These studies were used for a comparison of toxicity between jet engine particles and diesel exhaust particles.

The 13 papers can be subdivided into toxicological studies (5), epidemiological studies (5) and reviews (3). Overall, the epidemiological studies are cohorts working in or living nearby airports for long term effects or volunteer studies looking at short term exposures and markers of effects. The toxicological studies use either an engine rig or sample close to the exhaust of a jet engine airplane. Most studies focused on the particulate matter fraction with additional chemical analysis of the chemicals bound to the particles. Only two studies also provide information on the gaseous phase.

Toxicological studies

The five toxicological studies focused on particles and their effect on inflammation, cytotoxicity and genotoxicity either in mice or human bronchial or dendritic cells. The comparison is complicated by the fact that for each study different engines have been used, as well as differences in the operation and test cycle, the type of fuel used and the health effect markers. Due to this variation and the small sample of studies no pattern could be identified in the different types and settings of jet engines and their particle formation and subsequent effect on toxicity. Within studies the following observations were noted:

- Exposure to JEP from conventional Jet A-1 aviation fuel induced more LDH release and oxidative stress compared to 32% v v⁻¹ hydroprocessed esters and fatty acids (HEFA) blend fuel while HEFA blend caused increased cytokine release (Jonsdottir, Delaval et al. 2019).
- Jet engine particles at low thrust can promote the production of IL-6 and IL-8 mainly at the highest applied dose; whereas for jet engine at high thrust few effects were observed (He, Gerlofs-Nijland et al. 2020).

In general, JEP caused pulmonary inflammatory responses in *in vitro* cell lines as well as *in vivo* (mouse). In dendritic cells derived from human blood, exposure to JEP induced little effect on human immature expression of costimulatory molecules but JEP synergize with lipopolysaccharide to induce distinct maturation patterns (Ferry, Rolland et al. 2011).

Some studies also tested ambient airport UFP (Bendtsen, Brostrøm et al. 2019, He, Gerlofs-Nijland et al. 2020), airport and urban PM_{2.5} as well as diesel exhaust particles (He, Shirmohammadi et al. 2018) and diesel exhaust particles and carbon black (Bendtsen, Brostrøm et al. 2019) in addition to the JEP in their study. For an extensive recent review on the toxicity of JEP, expected health effects and its comparison with diesel exhaust particles and other traffic emissions see below the review of (Bendtsen, Bengtsen et al. 2021).

Epidemiological studies

Five papers were identified that related aircraft emissions to health effects. Habre et al. (Habre, Zhou et al. 2018) compared respiratory and inflammatory markers in individuals after a 2-hour walk inside and outside a high airport-related ultrafine particle zone. Airport UFP exposure increased a systemic inflammation marker (IL-6) as did exposure to more traffic-related air pollution (sTNFrII). Traffic-related air pollution also induced a decrease in FEV1. Lammers et al (Lammers, Janssen et al. 2020) exposed healthy volunteers for five hours a day on several occasions to ambient air near Schiphol Airport while performing intermittent moderate exercise. They concluded that short-term exposure to high levels of UFP near Schiphol Airport was, on average, associated with decreased lung function (mainly FVC) and prolonged repolarization of the heart (QTc), directly after exposure in young healthy adults. The effects were relatively small, however, they appeared already after single exposures of 5 h in a young healthy population. Wing et al (Wing, Larson et al. 2020) looked at the effect of *in utero* exposure to UFP from aircraft emissions in a 15 km area around Los Angeles International Airport and found that exposure of pregnant women to aircraft UFP was associated with a higher risk of pre-term birth. Two studies looked at occupational exposure to aircraft emissions and increased incidence of health effects. Yang et al (Yang, Wu et al. 2003) used a cross-sectional study among airport workers versus terminal or office workers at the Kaohsiung International Airport. They found that occupational exposure to aviation fuel or exhaust is associated with an excess of some chronic adverse respiratory symptoms (cough and dyspnea) in male airport workers. Møller et al (Møller, Brauer et al. 2020) conducted a follow-up cohort study in airport workers at Copenhagen Airport for 22 years and looked at cardiovascular effects (ischemic heart disease (IHD) and cerebrovascular disease) with cumulated apron-years as exposure proxy. No association was found between occupational exposure at Copenhagen Airport and IHD and cerebrovascular disease.

Reviews

Three reviews were identified. Merzenich et al (Merzenich, Riccetti et al. 2021) focused on the impact of air pollution on airport apron workers and could only identify three epidemiological studies. Two cross-sectional studies were of limited relevance due to small sample size and a lack of quantitative exposure data. These studies indicated an association between high exposure and respiratory symptoms like runny nose, cough and dyspnoea. In a relatively large cohort study which included a quantitative exposure assessment, no association was found between cumulative apron-years and incidence of ischemic heart disease or cerebrovascular disease during a mean follow-up of 14.4 years. Touri et al. (2013) reached a similar conclusion reviewing the impact of airport pollution on respiratory health at work. They concluded that very few studies have established an association between pollution in an airport work environment and respiratory problems (like coughing, shortness of breath, wheezing, decreased lung function, runny nose). Generally, the correlation was weak because there is a lack of power, a lack of precision over the types of jobs affected, a lack of quantitative exposure data, and the presence of many confounding factors. No study included in their review has demonstrated a significant relationship between specific exposure to jet exhaust particles and respiratory symptoms.

The most comprehensive review was performed by Bendtsen et al (2021). The authors summarize the available exposure, epidemiological and toxicological data related to jet engine

emissions in and around airports. The epidemiological study results in this review suggest that the exposure to aircraft emissions induce pulmonary and systemic inflammation, which potentially contributes to cancer, asthma, respiratory and coronary heart disease. From the toxicological mechanistical studies, the conclusions from the *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies support the overall concern that airport emission particles are capable of inducing toxic responses comparable to the responses observed for other air pollution particles such as diesel exhaust particles.

Regarding particle characteristics two important reported characteristics of airport particles are highlighted:

- The majority of non-volatile airport emission particles are carbonaceous and aircraft engines emit large amounts of nanoparticles, which are dominated by very small particles of < 20 nm, which form aggregates/agglomerates in ambient air.
- Particle numbers near airports are significantly higher than away from airports and jet engines are a significant source of UFP in ambient air. The highest concentrations of UFP are measured downwind of aircraft.

Overall, Bendsten et al (2021) conclude that though the literature is scarce and with low consistency in methods and measured biomarkers, there is evidence that jet engine emissions have physicochemical properties similar to diesel exhaust particles, and that exposure to jet engine emissions is associated with similar adverse health effects as exposure to diesel exhaust particles and other traffic emissions. However, given the lack of consensus on optimal measurement methods, equipment and quality control for near- and far field airport emissions and human risk assessments markers, more studies of exposure and of toxicological mechanisms are necessary.

Comparison with road traffic particulate matter emissions

In an *in vitro* study (He, Shirmohammadi et al. 2018) human bronchial epithelial cells were exposed to particulate matter from a jet engine (Fighting Falcon) as well as a low-sulfur fuel diesel engine. In addition, ambient air particulate matter (PM_{0.25}) was collected at a major airport or near major freeways. Particles showed little cytotoxic effects with the exception of some of samples of ambient air particles (2 out of 5 PM samples) collected near major freeways, which induced ~20% decrease in cell viability. No significant induction and release of inflammatory mediators (IL-8) were seen for both jet engine and diesel engine exhaust particles, whereas ambient air particles near a major airport induced a higher release of inflammatory mediators (IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α) when compared to PM samples collected near major freeways and to unexposed controls. Although chemical analysis (EC/OC content and elemental composition) indicated differences in composition of PM from the various sources, it is unclear (if and) how these differences can explain the observed differences in cytotoxicity and cytokine induction.

So far, the only *in vivo* study (Bendtsen, Brostrøm et al. 2019) exposed mice via intratracheal instillation with a 1, 28 or 90 day follow up on inflammatory and genotoxicity effects. Next to jet engine particles, they also exposed mice to reference particles Printex 90 (carbon black) and NIST2975 (standard reference material for diesel exhaust particles). The physicochemical

characterization showed that JEP were primarily agglomerated carbon nanoparticles with levels of metals and PAH comparable to those found in the standard diesel particles. JEP induced acute phase responses as well as time- and dose-dependent cytological changes in BAL cell composition, which were similar to the responses observed for NIST2975 and CB, and to previously published results for NIST1650. JEP and NIST2975 induced increased levels of DNA strand breaks across doses and time points. Based on these results the authors conclude that the study suggests that jet engine particles have similar physicochemical properties and toxicity as diesel exhaust particles.

In addition to that study, Bendtsen also performed these *in vivo* toxicological experiments with different diesel exhaust particles (designed to differ in physicochemical properties) in a separate study (Bendtsen, Gren et al. 2020). Generally, the observed toxicity was similar to the findings in the abovementioned study with jet engine and diesel exhaust particles (Bendtsen, Brostrøm et al. 2019). In a comparison between the different diesel exhaust particles, intratracheal exposure to the various particles induced similar toxicological responses, with different potency (details can be found in the database).

3.2 Oxidative potential

The results of the measurements of oxidative potential (OP) of PM samples collected by ONERA and Cardiff University are given in the table below (Table 6).

Table 6: Oxidative potential measurements of PM samples.

Sample code	Fuel type	ESR (AU)	AAdep _{max} (nmol/sec)	DTT _{cons} (nmol DTT/ug PM*min)
Samples collected by ONERA using RIVM filters:				
RAPTOR 5	blank	4453	0.689	-0.001
RAPTOR 8	blank	4316	0.551	-0.010
RAPTOR 1	Jet A1 High ARO, high S	5898	1.412	0.074
RAPTOR 2	Jet A1 High ARO, high S	5451	0.598	0.015
RAPTOR 3	AtJ	5865	1.388	0.085
RAPTOR 4	Jet A1 High ARO	2894	0.660	0.065
RAPTOR 6	Jet A1 high S	3795	0.426	0.072
RAPTOR 7	Jet A1 reference	4028	0.397	0.052
RAPTOR 9	Jet A1	3236	0.709	0.079
RAPTOR 10	Jet A1 / AtJ	2744	0.466	0.050
RAPTOR 11	Jet A1 High ARO, high S	2726	0.420	0.043
RAPTOR 12	SPK	4843	0.868	0.040
Solvent blank		3591	0.521	0.012
Pos control		50545	5.722	0.123
Neg control		3481	0.379	n/a
Samples collected by ONERA using TNO filters:				
EU-21	blank	9298	0.545	0.020
EU-57	blank	4206	0.504	0.009
EU-43	blank of line	11660	0.932	0.107
EU-04	Jet A1 high S	7860	0.298	0.095
EU-23	Jet A1 High ARO	8886	0.404	0.088

EU-42	Jet A1 reference	8519	0.347	0.025
EU-53	Jet A1 / AtJ	7431	0.386	0.098
EU-51	Jet A1	7306	0.440	0.117
EU-55	Jet A1 High ARO, high S	7488	0.502	0.100
EU-60	SPK	9350	0.724	0.050
Pos control		1	4.688	0.120
Neg control		1	0.301	n/a
Samples collected by Cardiff University:				
EU-01	filter blank	4405	1.055	0.016
EU-31	blank of line	3795	0.865	0.029
EU-33	SAF J2 (F4)	4584	2.119	0.058
EU-35	Jet A	3090	0.810	0.019
EU-39	B3	2775	0.733	0.035
EU-41	F1	2911	0.705	0.042
EU-45	75% GTL	3566	0.932	0.066
EU-47	100% GTL	6629	1.187	0.081
EU-49	B3	2433	2.161	0.077
Pos ctrl		1	2	0.137
Neg control		1	2	n/a

n/a: not applicable (DTT data are automatically adjusted for negative control readings)

¹ See positive/negative control data of ONERA samples using RIVM filters (all samples were analyzed in a single run, so only one positive and negative control sample was needed).

² See positive/negative control data of ONERA samples using RIVM filters (which were analyzed on the same 96-well plate and it was therefore not necessary to include separate controls).

The above results are plotted in Figure 5.

No clear differences in OP levels between the various PM samples were detected in any of the assays. OP_{ESR} levels of PM samples were generally in the same range as untreated blank filters; samples taken by ONERA using TNO filters showed slightly higher OP_{ESR} levels, but these were comparable with the “blank of line” sample. OP_{AA} levels were also comparable to blank levels for almost all PM samples; a few samples showed somewhat higher values, but there was no clear trend in the fuel type used to generate these samples. In the DTT assay, most PM samples showed higher OP levels when compared to untreated blank samples – at least for samples collected by ONERA – but there was no clear difference between the various fuel types. The positive control samples showed the expected results in all three assays, which were in line with historical control data (kept in the RIVM archives). Overall, these analyses of oxidative potential did not reveal any clear differences in reactivity of PM generated by combustion of the fuel types investigated in this study. Because of the lack of a clear trend in these oxidative potential results, it was decided – also given the limited amount of PM sample remaining – not to repeat the measurements or to further investigate (acellular) oxidative potential; statistical analysis of the present data is therefore not possible (but also not considered useful given the outcomes). Remaining PM material was stored for possible further analysis. In addition to the oxidative potential investigations foreseen in RAPTOR, the toxicity of PM samples is currently being assessed using human 3D cell models. Co-cultures of human bronchial epithelial cells and macrophages are being exposed to PM in an air-liquid interface (ALI) exposure system. Toxicity will be assessed in terms of cytotoxicity, compromised epithelial barrier function, intracellular ROS generation, production of inflammatory markers, and DNA damage. The results of these *in vitro* toxicity experiments are not yet available.

Figure 5: Oxidative potential of PM samples collected by ONERA using RIVM filters (A), by ONERA using TNO filters (B), or by Cardiff University (C). Oxidative potential was measured as consumed dithiothreitol (DTT, in nmol DTT/ $\mu\text{g PM} \cdot \text{min}$, in gray), or ascorbic acid (AAdep, in nmol/sec, in orange) or by electron spin resonance (ESR, in arbitrary units, in blue). The data in table 6 were scaled to fit on the same y-axis (ESR data were divided by 10;

*AAdep data were multiplied by 1000; DTT data were multiplied by 10000). For the ESR and AAdep assay, the positive control levels are above the maximum indicated on the y-axis (see table 6 for the actual data). The dashed line represents the (average) result of the untreated blank filters of each assay. More details on the samples (e.g. fuel type) can be found in table 2. Positive control: Diesel Oil Fly Ash (DOFA). *Blank EU-21 was omitted, because contamination was found on the filter.*

3.3 Hazard assessment

The review by Bendsten et al (2021) identifies the current gaps in the literature which must be filled to allow for a proper hazard assessment of jet engine particles. In general, literature is scarce and with low consistency in methods and measured biomarkers. There are no studies on the toxicity of jet engine particles which also include a full physical and chemical characterization and systematic investigation of exposure variables and engine operating conditions. Although the few studies available suggest that jet engine particles share similar physicochemical properties to diesel exhaust particles with similar associated health effects (e.g. acute phase responses; cytological changes and DNA strand breaks in BAL cells after intratracheal instillation in mice), there remains a lack of data to allow for a hazard and risk assessment of exposure to jet engine particles. The present results of the oxidative potential measurements of PM generated by combustion of various jet fuels did not allow a differentiation of the different fuel types or engine conditions. Based on the literature on physical-chemical properties using different fuels it can be concluded that the reduction of low sulfur and aromatic content will result in reduced emission of PM and PM precursors. This will also result in lower toxicity assuming equal toxicity of the generated PM. In addition, high thrust will promote lower emission of total hydrocarbon and less production of inflammatory markers. For polyaromatic hydrocarbons, such as naphthalene as proxy for the total PAH mass, emissions increased as power increased. Though, although little is known about the toxicity of jet engine emissions, some recommendations can be made for the use of fuel that could promote a lower exposure. For example, fuels with a low sulfur and aromatics content have been shown to result in lower emissions of PM and PM precursors.

It was envisioned to predict the toxicity of various emission mixtures (for different operating conditions, engine and fuel types) based on knowledge on the toxic potency of key components in the mixture and information on interactions (synergy, antagonism). It was anticipated to derive this knowledge from literature, extended with data from RAPTOR and other recent and ongoing projects (such as [TUBE](#)). However, as described above, the currently available data do not allow for a proper hazard assessment. To our knowledge, other projects did not yet provide further (publicly available) data which could substantiate the hazard assessment either. Ideally, dose- (or concentration-) response relationships would be available for relevant toxicological endpoints, for a given emission mixture and its (toxicologically relevant) components. In combination with data on composition of the mixture (including size distribution), an aggregated hazard index can then be constructed incorporating the relative contribution to health effects, prioritized based on the estimated contribution to local PM concentrations.

4 Summary and conclusion

The aim of this work was to assess the hazard of jet engine exhaust, based on available literature and newly generated experimental data. A literature survey was performed, which was focussed on the physico-chemical composition of jet engine emissions, and on the toxicity of jet engine exhaust. The toxicity was put in perspective of toxicity data of road traffic PM emissions. In addition, oxidative potential measurements of collected PM samples were performed, aiming to support the hazard assessment.

The literature survey on the physical and chemical composition of jet engine emission resulted in an Excel-based file with emission indices of 12 different airplane engines. Per engine, the emission indices for each analyzed compound were sorted for different percentages of thrust. In additions, per engine, the results from different fuels were clustered, which allows for the comparison between different fuels. In general, no, or low, sulfur and low aromatic content is found to be beneficial to reduce the emission of PM and PM precursors. In terms of chemical composition, the total hydrocarbon emission indices are highest at low power settings. The emission of carbonyl compounds is significantly higher during the idle mode than at higher thrusts, similar to BTEX compounds which show large decreases in emissions with increasing engine power. In contrast, the emission index of naphthalene increases as power increases from idle mode falling off as the engine operated at the highest power.

The literature survey on toxicity data of jet engine emissions resulted in only four research papers; therefore relevant epidemiological studies and reviews were also included in the survey. The toxicological studies focused on particles and their effects on inflammation, cytotoxicity and genotoxicity and used mice (*in vivo*) or human bronchial or dendritic cells (*in vitro*) as experimental model. Variation in experimental set-up and the small sample of studies did not allow for the differentiation between the different types and settings of jet engines and their subsequent effect on toxicity. It was found that conventional Jet A-1 aviation fuel induced more cytotoxicity (LDH release) and oxidative stress compared to HEFA blend fuel, whilst the latter caused an increase in inflammatory mediators (cytokine release). Jet engine particles at low thrust promoted the production of IL-6 and IL-8 compared to a high thrust setting. Jet engine particles induced similar toxic responses in *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, when compared to urban PM or diesel exhaust particles.

The analysis of oxidative potential (OP) did not reveal any clear differences in reactivity of PM samples generated by combustion of the fuel types investigated in this study. In the Electron Spin Resonance and Ascorbic Acid Depletion assays, OP levels of PM samples were generally in the same range as untreated blank filters. In the DTT assay, most PM samples showed higher OP levels when compared to untreated blank samples, but there was no clear difference between the various fuel types.

Due to the lack of toxicity data (only one *in vivo* study available) of jet engine particles produced under different settings (engine type; fuel and thrust) no hazard index could be constructed. The generated oxidative potential data in this project did not allow for a differentiation in toxicity based on oxidative potential. Based on the literature on physical-chemical properties using different fuels it can be concluded that the reduction of low sulfur and aromatic content will result in reduced emission of PM and PM precursors. This will also

result in lower toxicity assuming equal toxicity of the generated PM. In addition, high thrust will promote lower emission of total hydrocarbon and less production of inflammatory markers. However, for polyaromatic hydrocarbons such as naphthalene, emissions increased as power increased. Obviously, to allow for a proper hazard assessment of jet engine emissions, more systematic toxicological research is needed in combination with the physical-chemical properties of the jet engine exhaust.

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6 Annexes

- Annex 1: Details of the PM sampling campaign performed by ONERA

7 Additional files

- Public formatted data table RAPTOR D6.1 Emission database (Excel file)
- Public formatted data table RAPTOR D6.1 Combined Physico-chemical and Toxicity database (Excel file)

A short resume of UNREAL Campaign (November/ December 2021)

Description:

UNREAL: Unveiling Nucleation mechanism in aiRcraft Engine exhAust and its Link with fuel composition

The UNREAL project aims to study at the molecular level the different mechanisms of new particle formation in the exhausts of aircraft engines feed by different fuel composition. This is especially important given the actual concern of aviation industry to reduce the impact of aviation on climate and air quality, and one of the envisaged means for that is the use of different sustainable aviation fuels. With this aim, two measurements campaigns were performed in the CESAM atmospheric chamber in 2020 (the first one in February and the second one in November). In these campaigns we used a Combustion Aerosol STandard (CAST) generator especially designed to work with liquid fuel (Jing 2003) to test fuels with different composition, from the standard Jet-A1 to 100% SAF (Alcohol to Jet). Emissions from CAST were injected in the chamber to study their chemical and physical evolution by different instruments sampling directly from the CESAM chamber: that included SMPS, LII, PTR-MS, ACMS-ToF, GC-FID, FTIR etc. During the second campaign (November) we added a Potentiel Aerosol Mass (PAM) flow reactor to compare evolution of emissions through the PAM (for a particular time) and in the chamber (over time). They were allowed to age in the presence of NO_x, light and OH tracers. A particular attention was given to the formation of additional particulate organic mass as well as new particle formation. In addition to on-line techniques, different sets of filters were taken to study chemical composition by L2MS and Tof-SIMS, and to investigate the ice nucleation properties of these particles (Netherlands laboratory).

Objectives of the thesis:

- Understand the different mechanisms involve in volatile Particles Matters (vPM) formation
- Links between fuel and aeronautics emissions and consequence for the evolution in the atmosphere

Setup:

- Mini CAST burner
- for liquid fuel
- operating principle based on the propane model to vaporize the fuel in the combustion chamber, which ignites at the top of this chamber
- A flow of nitrogen stops the combustion reaction and a flow of dilution air accelerates emissions in the measurement line
- Dilution of the emissions with a FPS (still waiting dilution factor from our partner INERIS) before the PAM

During the two campaigns, we realized injection of emissions in the CESAM chamber. After the injection, we worked continuously with the PAM or on CAST Raw to characterize the emissions and to take filters (after CESAM chamber, after the PAM reactor and directly on CAST Raw).

Figure 1 Experimental set up with CAST/CESAM and CAST/PAM

Fuel Matrix:

Fuel	Aromatic content (%)	Sulfur content (ppm)
Jet A1 reference	16	4
Jet A1 High aromatic compounds	23	4
Jet A1 High Sulfur compounds	16	3000
Jet A1 High aromatic compounds & Sulfur compounds	23	3000
Jet A1	15,5	200
Alcohol to Jet (AtJ)	0	0
Jet A1/AtJ blend	10,8	140
SPK	2.5	0

Experiment:

We tested a different fuel every two days. The first day we did an injection with only gas phases in the chamber (soot filtered with HEPA filter in entrance of the chamber). The second day we did an injection with gas+soot in the chamber.

In the both case, there were no dilution before injection, injection lasted some minutes and lights were on 30min after injection.

Filters:

During the campaign, different kind of filters were done:

- ONERA/PhLAM filters to sample in two separate filters the particles phase and the gas phase (Ngo, 2020)
- INAR filters INAR (Finland) to study the crystallization of ice particles
- TNO and RIVM filters (Netherlands) to study the impact of emissions on health (measurement of the oxidation potential)

Concerning TNO and RIVM, we took alternatively these filters directly on CAST RAW:

Conditions of sampling are indicated in the following table:

Date	Fuel	Name	Sampling time	Flow(L/min)	CAST conditions
23/11/2020	23% ARO + 3000ppm S	RIVM	15sec	49	105/30/2
	23% ARO + 3000ppm S	RIVM	1min	10	105/30/2
24/11/2020	AtJ	RIVM	5min	2.2	105/30/2
25/11/2020	23% ARO + 4ppm S	RIVM	5min	2.2	105/30/2
27/11/2020	16% ARO + 3000ppm S	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	105/30/2
27/11/2020	16% ARO + 3000ppm S	RIVM	30sec	29.8	105/30/2
02/12/2020	Blank	TNO	All the night	0	105/30/2
03/12/2020	23% ARO + 4ppm S	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	105/30/2
	16% ARO + 4ppm S	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	105/30/2
	16% ARO + 4ppm S	RIVM	5min	2.2	105/30/2
04/12/2020	Blank of line	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	105/30/2
07/12/2020	Jet A1 (16% ARO + 200ppm S)	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	84/30/3
	Jet A1 (16% ARO + 200ppm S)	RIVM	5min	2.2	84/30/3
08/12/2020	E5 (70% Jet A1 + 30% AtJ)	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	84/30/3
	E5 (70% Jet A1 + 30% AtJ)	RIVM	5min	2.2	84/30/3
09/12/2020	23% ARO + 3000ppm S	RIVM	5min	2.2	84/30/3
	23% ARO + 3000ppm S	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	84/30/3
10/12/2020	SPK	TNO	1min30	7.4/4.6/6.9	84/30/3
	SPK	RIVM	5min	2.2	84/30/3

(ARO for aromatics compounds and S for sulfur)

Between 18 November and 7 December, we worked with CAST parameters: $Q_{\text{fuel}}=105\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ / $Q_{\text{propane}}=30\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ / $Q_{\text{air}}=2\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. And between 7 December and 10 December, we changed for $Q_{\text{fuel}}=84\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ / $Q_{\text{propane}}=30\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ / $Q_{\text{air}}=3\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

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